

Complexes of 2-(2'-Pyridyl) benzimidazole with Chromium and Manganese

S. P. GHOSH

Chemical Laboratory, Patna University, Patna 800005.

AND

A. MISHRA

Chemical Laboratory, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur 812007.

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2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole (LH) forms (a) with chromium(III), a binuclear complex $[\text{CrL}_2\text{X}]_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , (b) with manganese(IV), $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, and (c) with manganese(II), complexes of the general formulae: (i) $\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- ; (ii) $\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , SCN^- , ClO_4^- , $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, and (iii) $\text{Mn}(\text{LH})\text{L}_2$. These have been isolated in solid states and characterised.

COORDINATION compounds of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole ($\text{LH} = \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$) with several metals have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁶. The chelating properties of this biologically important imidazole derivative has been a subject of investigation in these laboratories and recently^{7,8} a large number of complexes, isolated in solid state, have been reported with Fe(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Co(III), Cu(II), Ni(II), Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Ir(III). In that sequence we report here the complexes of chromium and manganese.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole immediately reacts with chromium(II) halide in an ethanolic medium to form a deep olive green solution, from which no solid could be isolated. On aerial oxidation of the above, a bis-chelated halobridged binuclear complex of chromium(III), $[\text{CrL}_2(\text{X})]_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br), separated as a yellow solid. The disappearance of the N-H stretching frequency in the i.r. spectrum of the complex confirms that the imidazole N-H has been deprotonated. As expected, the complex shows only negligible electrical conductance.

Manganese(III) acetate reacts with a hydrochloric acid solution of the ligand to form a deep red solution, from which a chocolate black crystalline perchlorate, $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, has been isolated. A strong absorption band near 3090 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectrum shows that the imidazole N-H is not affected. The bands at 1598 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} (with a spreading of 228 cm^{-1}) are due to CO stretch in the monodentate acetate ions⁹; the band at $1090-1130\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to $\nu_3-\text{ClO}_4$ (uncoordinated). According to the present formulation, the metal appears to be in +4-oxidation state, but room tem-

perature magnetic moment value (3.4 B.M.) is rather low.

The above acetato-complex has been found to be instantaneously reduced to yellow $\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2(\text{SCN})_2$, having μ_{eff} value of 5.99 B.M., by mere interaction with potassium thiocyanate. Detailed investigation shows that the following three types of manganese(II) complexes are produced, depending more or less on the metal : ligand ratio used in the preparations.

(a) 1 : 1 Complex. The four-coordinated $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ or Br^- , is formed as a pale yellow solid when the ligand is refluxed with an excess of manganese(II) halide in dry ethanol. Magnetic moment and electrical conductance support the suggested formula.

(b) 1 : 2 Complex. The six-coordinated $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ or Br^- , separates as yellow solid when the metal halide is refluxed with the ligand in 1 : 2 molar proportion in dry ethanol. When ammonium thiocyanate is added to the above solution, the thiocyanato-complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$, is obtained, which may be equated with the one obtained by reduction of the acetato-complex (*vide infra*) on the basis of their identical magnetic moment values and superimposable i.r. spectra. The N-H stretching band appears near 3050 cm^{-1} and a strong CN stretching vibration at 2075 cm^{-1} . The CS stretching frequency in the region $700-800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is obscured by ligand vibrations. Perchlorate ion, however, does not enter the coordination zone, as treatment of the yellow solution of metal chloride (1 mole) and ligand (2 moles) with sodium perchlorate yields a yellow precipitate of the formula $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$. The free ionic perchlorate is confirmed by the molar conductance value and also by the appearance of a broad absorption band at $1050-1125\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The yellowish white solid $Mn(LH)_2SO_4$, obtained on treatment of hot aqueous manganese(II) sulphate with ethanolic ligand, is insoluble in common solvents and, as such, no investigation could be made in that case.

(c) 1 : 3 Complex. In the presence of an excess of ammonium chloride, the yellow solution of the ligand with an excess of manganese(II) chloride gives a water-insoluble inner-complex $[Mn(LH)L_2]$ when the pH is maintained at ~ 6 with the help of very dilute ammonia solution. Examples of co-existence of protonated and deprotonated ligands in the same complex molecule are also found in the work of Chiswell *et al.*¹⁰ in the case of cobalt(II) complexes with several ligands.

No information could be obtained from the electronic absorption spectra of the complexes as they show continuous absorption with charge-transfer in the ultra-violet region. Similar observations were recorded earlier with several complexes of other metal ions with this ligand^{7,8}.

Experimental

Materials. Chromium(II) salts were prepared in solution by dissolving electrolytic chromium (99.999% pure)* in 1 : 1 hydrochloric or hydrobromic acid in nitrogen atmosphere. Manganese(II) salts used were all E. Merck's 'pro analysi' grade, except manganese(II) bromide, which was prepared by precipitating the carbonate from manganese(II) chloride and then converting it to bromide. Manganese(III) acetate was prepared by oxidising manganese(II) acetate with potassium permanganate in acetic acid medium¹¹. The ligand was obtained by the method of Leko and Vlajinats¹.

Preparation of Complexes

μ -Dihalo-tetrakis{2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazolato}-dichromium(III) An ethanolic solution of the ligand (slightly less than 2 moles) was added to chromium(II) chloride or bromide (1 mole) solution in aqueous ethanol in nitrogen atmosphere when a deep olive green solution was obtained. It was oxidised by passing a brisk current of air and the colour changed to wine-red. On dilution with water and addition of a dilute solution of sodium acetate, a flocculent yellow precipitate was obtained, which was purified by reprecipitation from ethanol and finally dried in air.

Diacetatobis {2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(IV) perchlorate. 2-(2'-Pyridyl) benzimidazole (0.9 g) was suspended in water (50 ml) and dissolved by the addition of minimum volume of 1 : 1 HCl. Manganese(III) acetate (1.6 g; large excess than stoichiometry to avoid the precipitation of ligand perchlorate at a later stage) was added in small instalments with

constant stirring. This was filtered and the filtrate was treated with a concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate when a dark brown solid separated. This was recrystallised from water in presence of sodium perchlorate, washed with ice-cold water and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$.

Dihalo {2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(II) It separated as a pale yellow solid when ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.5 g) was refluxed for about 30 min with a similar solution of a large excess of manganese(II) halide (1 g). The solid was washed with hot ethanol and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$.

Dihalo-bis {2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(II). A yellow solid which separated by refluxing the metal halide (1 mole) and the ligand (in slight excess of 2 moles) as above, was washed with hot ethanol and dried in air.

Dithiocyanatobis {2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(II). This compound precipitated when (i) the deep wine-red solution of manganese(III) acetate in dilute HCl solution of the ligand was treated with a concentrated solution of potassium thiocyanate, or (ii) the yellow solution of the above mentioned 1 : 2 halo-complex was treated with ammonium thiocyanate. The solid was washed thoroughly with water and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$.

Bis{2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(II) perchlorate. On account of the tendency of the ligand to be precipitated as perchlorate, manganese was kept in sufficient excess. Manganese(II) chloride and the ligand (1 : 1 molar proportion) were heated to boiling in ethanol and then treated with a solution of sodium perchlorate. A yellow precipitate separated, which was washed with water and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$ and KOH.

Bis{2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(II) sulphate. This was obtained as a yellowish white solid when a hot aqueous solution of an excess of metal sulphate was treated with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand. The solid was washed several times with hot water and finally with ethanol and dried over $CaCl_2$.

Bis{2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazolato} {2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole} manganese(II). The yellow solution containing ligand and metal chloride in excess was treated with an aqueous solution containing a large excess of ammonium chloride and then the pH of the solution was carefully raised to ~ 6 with the help of very dilute ammonia solution. A yellow crystalline mass separated after some time, which was washed with water and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$ and KOH.

Physical measurements. Magnetic measurements were made in a Gouy magnetic balance calibrated¹² with $Hg Co(SCN)_4$; diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants¹³. Electrical conductances were measured with a WTW Conductivity Bridge, type LBR. Infra-red spectra were recorded with the help of a Perkin Elmer 237 spectrometer

*Electrolytic chromium was obtained as a generous gift from M/S Schmelztechnik, Munchen.

TABLE
ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCES AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS

Compound	Elemental Analyses										Conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹ (temp. °C in parentheses) Solvent* A or B	Magnetic Moments	
	% Metal		% C		% H		% N		% Anion			T	μ _B
	found	reqd.	found	reqd.	found	reqd.	found	reqd.	found	reqd.			
[CrL ₂ Cl] ₂ ·10H ₂ O	7.89	7.93					12.66	12.82	5.48	5.41	15.6(31)A	304.4	3.74
[CrL ₂ Br] ₂ ·5H ₂ O	8.42	8.49					14.13	13.72	12.91	13.05			
[Mn(LH) ₂ (AcO) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	6.65	7.20	45.12	44.10	3.28	3.17	11.37	11.02				303.0	3.38
[Mn(LH)Cl] ₂	17.06	17.11	45.04	44.88	3.03	2.83	13.37	13.09	21.86	22.08	25.7(25)B		
[Mn(LH)Br] ₂	15.29	15.40					10.42	10.25	39.05	38.98		296.5	5.91
[Mn(LH) ₂ Cl ₂].H ₂ O	10.57	10.28	54.45	53.94	3.87	3.77	15.66	15.73	13.63	13.58	25.7(25)B	295.8	6.14
[Mn(LH) ₂ Br ₂]	8.86	9.07					13.87	13.89	26.34	26.41			
[Mn(LH) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	9.74	9.83					20.24	20.06				304.4	5.99
[Mn(LH) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	8.31	8.52					13.32	13.04			116.0(26)B		
Mn(LH) ₂ SO ₄	10.06	10.14					15.06	15.52	17.65	17.74		296.8	6.11
[Mn(LH)L ₂]	8.22	8.14	64.27	64.08	4.09	4.33	18.67	18.68			10.6(26)B	302.2	6.03

* Solvents : A = Aqueous ethanol; B = Dimethylformamide.

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